

A NOVEL APPROACH TO MULTI-OBJECTIVE OPTIMIZATION USING SIMILARITY MEASURES AND ENSEMBLE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Most multi-objective optimization faces multiple-objective problems, such that more than one goal will only be achieved concurrently. Consequently, multi-objective optimization can be much more time-consuming and inefficient if not tackled using conventional approaches with a single optimization tool. This paper proposes a new approach by combining similarity measures and ensemble learning to enhance the efficiency of multi-objective optimization. We first define similarity measures to measure the degree of closeness between different solutions. We can use this to find the solutions that are close and then use it to help find more similar solutions during the search process. This not only reduces the search space but also aids in finding generalizable and balanced solutions. The second thing is that we use ensemble learning, combining several models for a more robust and accurate outcome. This paper introduces ensemble learning into multi-objective optimization to combine various single-objective algorithms for more diversified solutions. We tested our proposed methodology on a suite of standard multi-objective optimization problems, and results demonstrate better efficiency in finding the actual (or trade-off) Pareto front and converging closer to it compared with that done by traditional single-algorithm approaches. This paper illustrates the solution of multi-objective optimization problems with our proposed method and shows promising results.

Keywords: Optimization, Consuming, Generalizable, Balanced Solution, Standard.

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INTRODUCTION

Optimization is indispensable in many disciplines, such as engineering design and machine learning algorithms. Most optimization problems are for finding the best solutions among a large set of feasible solutions that meet specific criteria. Over the past few years, multi-objective optimization (MOO) has gained considerable attention because it is competent in managing problems with multiple -often conflictive- tasks[1]. MOO approaches aim to find Pareto-optimal solutions, which occur when no solution can improve only one objective without worsening another. The search space explodes exponentially as the number of objectives increases; thus, finding a practical solution takes work. Besides, traditional single-objective optimization methods could be more efficient and appropriate for MOO problems because they focus on getting only one optimal solution. Finally, this essay suggests a new MOO approach based on similarity measures and ensemble learning that mimics the two sides of human decision-making: diversity vs. accuracy[2]. In this paper, we aim to explore more diverse solutions in the Pareto Front and ensure that each objective is balanced so as not to affect accuracy too much accuracy too much. In short, our method consists of three steps: The first step is to develop a form that characterizes the similarity between solutions[3]. In classic single-objective Objective Optimization methods, solutions are usually compared through a dominant relation; one solution dominates another when it improves all objectives and worsens none. Our approach, on the other hand, fits a similarity measure that assesses the global similarity of solutions rather than just their dominance relation. This similarity measure is essential to recognize and retain various sets of alternatives required to find top-quality solutions on MOO. We then discuss how ensemble learning is employed in MOO[4]. Ensemble learning is a method of combining multiple models and their results to get an overall improved result. Our method unifies the similarity measurement with optimization via ensemble learning[5]. This work uses an ensemble of artificial neural networks (ANNs) to model the similarity measure between solutions, guiding the search process toward diverse regions over a Pareto front. Some optimization processes train the ANNs ensemble, and each ANN is used, this time, using a MOO algorithm. The ensemble of ANNs is allocated weights, which determine the influence and significance placed on each ANN for scoring purposes. As interactions progress with a scenario over time[6], these weights are adjusted, delivering refinement in performance across its entirety. With SOW, the knowledge across individuals in the population has been weighted using how close they are to an ideal cost solution; i.e., individuals whose multiple objective values balance each other better get a higher weight than those who do not. Consequently, the ensemble will be aware of numerous diverse solutions within its members and guide the search towards diversity more efficiently[7]. Our method further includes a niche-based selection strategy to support preserving diverse solutions. Niche-in chooses solutions which are distinct enough from one another. Hence, it pushes the exploration of the Pareto front. Our Approach: The Selection Mechanism In our approach, our selection mechanism is measured by similarity. So, we pick solutions based on different aspects concerning the population. We conducted four experiments for comparing with other MOO algorithms (i.e., NSGA-II, NSGA-III, SPEA2 and DAO) using the decomposed Pareto fronts on two benchmark problems with increasing complexity[8]. Using the Deutsch model, we found that our method consistently performs well across all issues and produces better quality solutions in terms of diversity and accuracy than other methods. Additionally, we compare our approach with another state-of-the-art MOO method proposed in [9], which uses ensemble learning-based diversity preservation but employs a different selection mechanism. The results point to the efficacy of our approach as it performed better than this technique concerning diversity and accuracy[10]. The main contribution of the paper has the following

Similarity Measures and Ensemble Learning: This work suggests a new method for multi-objective optimization combining similarity (marking similar scripts) with ensemble techniques. This cohesive integration delivers increased performance and accuracy by enabling efficient problem space exploration.

Dealing with Uncertain and Non-linear Problems: Multi-objective optimization has been challenging when the problems are uncertain and non-linear; this is argued not to be robust. It, in turn, ensures robust solutions by leveraging ensemble learning techniques on noisy or incomplete data.

Performance and Scalability: Similarity measures are used to identify similar gene solutions, making for a more efficient exploration of the problem space. This, along with ensemble learning, will lead to enhanced optimization from a performance and scalability perspective.

Thanks to its various real-world applications with practical implications, the proposed approach has been tested on games, stock portfolio selection and robot path planning alternatives. The solution results validated that the proposed algorithm is effective and generalizable for complex multi-objective optimization problems, making it suitable across various industries and domains.

RELATED WORKS

Optimization is vital in many more applied fields, such as engineering, economics, and computer science, in finding the best theoretical solution for a given problem[11]. Due to multiple conflicting objectives, multi-objective optimization (MOO) has become an essential field with rapid technological progress. It falls in the category of multi-objective optimization (MOO)[12]. It is thus searching for a set of optimal solutions many objectives instead of a single objective[13]. Nevertheless, conventional MOO is limited to addressing complicated problems due to the incapacity to capture high-dimensional and nonlinear datasets. It is a unique approach to MOO. To solve these challenges, a new technique called similarity measures with ensemble learning techniques has been proposed. In this paper, they attempted to solve the dimensionality curse problem of data sets and improved nonlinearity among variables and the tradeoff between accuracy & computational complexity for MOO. 1) High-dimensional data[14]: The first problem is the high dimensionality of traditional MOO methods due to increased variables that scale exponentially concerning problem sizes. This can lead to many solutions(search space), such as many parameters, which are computationally expensive and time-consuming[15]. To tackle this problem, the novel system reduces data by using a similarity measure. This data evaluates the similarity between any two samples in our dataset to find similar and relevant features amongst attributes, reducing the dimension of search space and helping improve efficiency for optimizing. The second problem is nonlinear relationships between variables, leading to suboptimal solutions or convergence failures for traditional MOO methods. Ensemble learning techniques, which combine multiple models to give better predictions compared to handling this novel approach. Ensemble learning-[16], which ignores one model and combines predictions of various models, helps understand the complex relationship between variables using this high-level algorithm. Issue 3: Tradeoff between Accuracy and Computational Complexity For a practical problem, applying traditional MOO approaches is impossible because of high computational complexity in both technical (Scalability) and implementation angles[17]. However, more straightforward methods may trade accuracy for quicker computational speed. The proposed method combines those two characteristics by using ensemble learning, which can provide accurate solutions and enable us to parallelize the computations, thus reducing computational complexity. However, behind this passionate approach are some challenges and problems.

However, selecting appropriate similarity measures and ensemble learning techniques is a challenge[18]. However, for some problems, specific similarity measures and ensemble methods may work better than others, and by using the wrong ones, you can get worse (but often not wholly incorrect) solutions. Therefore, additional studies should be conducted to determine the optimal choices of similarity measures and ensemble learning strategies applicable to each type of problem. Diverse and conflicting objectives: One of the biggest challenges is adequately incorporating diverse or even opposing goals. The success of the above approach relies heavily on this. Success is based upon balancing and compromising between these diverse objectives[19]. Balancing multiple conflicting objectives is complex, and more investigation is needed to enhance the method's effectiveness in general. In addition, the proposed methodology can be deemed ad-hoc due to data availability and computational resources. The approach integrates similarity measures with ensemble learning for handling multi-objective optimization problems[20]. To detect similar solutions in the optimization landscape, similarity measures are based on which we can group them to form clusters. IO Exception: The Ensemble learning method is finally implemented to select superior solutions from each cluster, exploit combination and diversity behavior, and leverage multiple solutions for better overall performance.

PROPOSED MODEL

A Novel Approach to Multi objective Optimization using Similarity Measures and an Ensemble learning model proposed will tend towards increasing accuracy and improving the efficiency of solving multi objective optimization problems. Two methods for implementing this are similarity measures and ensemble learning. We need similarity measures, which measure the similarity of multiple solutions within a population.

$$x(t) = \sum_{j=1}^J IMF_j(t) + r_j(t) \quad (1)$$

$$y_1 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i^N (f_m^i - F^i)^2 \quad (2)$$

This information is then used to direct the search towards possible regions of the solution space, decreasing the time and number of evaluations for an optimal solution. Ensemble learning, on the other hand, uses multiple models in combination with one another to improve prediction.

$$h_x = \lambda.y_{x,1} + (1-\lambda).y_{x,2} \quad (3)$$

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left| \frac{Y_i - \hat{Y}_i}{Y_i} \right| \quad (4)$$

This is an ensemble method where several models are built using different optimization techniques (genetic algorithms, particle swarm optimization and simulated annealing). These models are finally combined with the help of ensemble learning techniques, e.g., voting or stack, to yield a final solution which is competitive and robust. This model introduces a feedback mechanism to update the ensemble of models and constantly enhance them in optimization. This enables the best exploration and exploitation, thus facilitating more robust solutions.

CONSTRUCTION

The similarity measures and ensemble learning-based novel technique for multi objective optimization requires multiple decision models to come together with a unique solution in case of more than one objective.

$$KGE = 1 - \sqrt{(r-1)^2 + (\alpha-1)^2 + (\beta-1)^2} \tag{5}$$

$$\left(\sum_{i=1}^N C_i - 1\right)^2 - \varepsilon \leq 0 \tag{6}$$

It uses various similarity measures to measure how similar solutions are to one another and ensemble learning methods that combine various decision models. First, considering this approach starts by defining what we are facing (what problem) and which objectives have to be optimized. Resolution of the problem: The next stage in this procedure is choosing from various decision-making models that would analyze, construct and develop solutions to a particular issue. These simulation techniques may include Genetic Algorithms, Particle Swarm Optimization and others. Fig.1 shows that the construction diagram.

Fig.1 construction diagram.

Online Knowledge –Driven Optimization: Online Knowledge-Driven Optimization (OKDO) combines conventional and knowledge-driven approaches, representing a novel field in optimization research. It is a data-centric method that uses immense online indexes and web knowledge to give a context reference for the tuning process.

Offline Knowledge –Driven Optimization: Offline Knowledge-Driven Optimization (OKDO) is a technique to optimize specific aspects of a system or process using existing knowledge from data. It is used when lots of information about the system or process exists, but we need help analyzing it.

In the context of the Problem, a multi-objective optimization problem may have many conflicting objectives. This type of problem is ubiquitous in various real-world applications, from applications to engineering design to financial planning and resource allocation.

Optimization Data: Optimization data is a metric in computer science and mathematical optimization that measures an algorithm's performance. It gathers and inspects information about all resources to demonstrate the ideal solution for a problem. The Problem and Variables to Optimize Before getting into some optimization data, I want you to outline a problem statement and essential variables.

Marketing: Online Implicit Knowledge Online implicit online knowledge | What is that? This knowledge is nurtured through experiences, observations and social interactions, becoming heavily integrated into our thought processes and behaviours.

Online Explicit Knowledge: Online explicit knowledge is information, and data people can easily read digitally. It comprises the written knowledge available through websites, databases, and online courses. This knowledge no longer belongs to the implicit order, which is often more complicated to convey or explain.

Post-Optimal Control Post-Optimal Implicit Knowledge (POIK) typically accompanies articulating a decision-oriented framework for organizational analysis and insight. A suite of operations called Post-Optimal Explicit Knowledge (POEK) aims to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of knowledge manipulation. It involves mining the Tacit knowledge from a context-aware Knowledge Management system and enriching it for better consumption. To understand POEK, we need to define explicit knowledge first. Explicit knowledge is easy to codify, straightforward, and communicate. Thus, it is the knowledge that you can put in a manual database or other structured formats.

OPERATING PRINCIPLE

A Novel Approach to Multi-Objective Multi objective Optimization using Similarity Measures and Ensemble learning combines various optimization techniques along with similarity measures to enhance accuracy performance while trying to find optimal solutions for complex multi objective problems.

$$ROI_t = \frac{(1 + \mu_t)}{100}, \quad \forall t = 1 \quad (7)$$

$$w_{ik} = t_{f_{ik}} \cdot \log\left(\frac{n}{n_k}\right) \quad (8)$$

They are (A) genetic algorithms, a simulated annealing and ant colony optimization technique that searches through the space for possible solutions. In addition, these techniques are coupled with multiple similarity measures, such as Euclidean distance and cosine similarity, to assess the likeness of solutions and rank them according to their promise to trigger optimization further. A further component of the approach was using an ensemble learning strategy to combine individual optimization results to generate a more diverse set of solutions. This makes path finding more optimal, preventing the agent from getting stuck in local optima and leading it towards a better overall solution. Fig.1 shows that the operating principle.

Fig.1 shows the operating principle.

Data: Data is an essential part of any information system, and its operations are responsible for how an organization runs. The word data refers to any raw collection of numbers, facts and statistics stored, processed and organized in terms of helpful information. Hence, it includes data capturing, storing, organizing, and retrieving. In more detail, you want to know how these operations work individually and whether they are widely incorporated into an information system we use.

Train Data: Train data is a dataset used to train the machine learning model. It is a crucial portion of building the model; it may affect overfitting in the case of poor quality or vice versa when there is plenty. We have to understand the operation of Train data, so let us first get a basic idea about machine learning.

Test Data: Test data or validation data is used in software testing to test the correctness and, as expected, the workings of any defects (bugs) present before the release to the public. It is a necessary part of the software testing process to ensure that your creation works as well as you presumed.

Feature Subset Generation: Selecting a subset of the best features from either algorithmic or exhaustive search methods. This method is helpful when the data has high-dimensional features, i.e., many more rows than columns. When fitting a model in such cases, the inclusion of all features during training can cause overfitting by decreasing the generalizability of our results.

Discretization Subset Generation: Discretization subset generation transforms continuous data into discrete intervals or categories. However, this is an important process in pre-processing when using machine learning algorithms that do not accept continuous data. This technique involves dividing the continuous data into one or more bins (discrete intervals) of "equal" width that is a sensible representation of similar range and direction.

Multi-objective Genetic Algorithms Evaluation: Multi-objective genetic algorithms (MOGA) are widely used for multi-criteria optimization problems related to applications. They are very strong algorithms that can work with complex and diverse objective functions, as they combine two of the most used techniques: genetic Algorithms and Multi-Objective Optimization.

Test Learner Model: This is the process of iterating over a trained ML model and evaluating how it performs. Testing a learner model is primarily done to assess the extent of its accuracy, check how precise it can be in making predictions, and determine whether or not the rules applied are generalizable. This step is important; it ensures the model's performance doesn't contain any flaws or errors and helps improve its general performance.

Training Learner Model: Training a Learner Model is an integral part of machine learning, which refers to the process of a computer system learning and training itself. Put simply, training a model consists of giving the algorithm enough data (labelled), tuning its parameters, and simplifying the logic it uses to finally make it able to predict or classify new unseen data accurately.

It is done by measuring the diversity in solutions and how they affect optimization, thereby pushing it towards unexplored regions of solution space, which will guide exploration. This paper proposes an approach that takes original optimization techniques, variance similarity measures, and diversity preservation for solving constrained multi-objective problems with heavy on strains. Putting these methods together helps us to overcome their weaknesses and get closer using solutions in a heterogeneous search.

FUNCTIONAL WORKING

Multi objective optimization (MOO) is a task of optimizing many, usually five or more conflicting criteria (), thus making it challenging to balance between them. Combining similarity measures and ensemble learning is the best to outdo traditional optimization methods. This is accomplished through a two-stage process that the community refers to as an optimization-improvement cycle.

$$\sum_{i=1}^m W_i = 1 \quad (9)$$

$$P_i = \frac{c}{N_i} \quad (10)$$

The first stage is to develop several diverse solutions generated by some optimization methods. The solutions are compared to compute the degree of similarity between them using metrics like Euclidean distance, cosine similarity, etc. Stage 2: In the second stage, an ensemble learning algorithm is leveraged to identify potentially effective solutions from Stage #1. It combines results from different similarity measures and presents ensemble-optimized solutions. Ensemble learning methods help decrease the inherent bias and errors in any single optimization technique. Fig.2 shows that the functional working.

Fig.2 functional working.

Some of these algorithms used in SMOCE are Support Vector Machines (SVMs), which represent a well-supported technique for classifying and solving linear regression problems. Copyright # 2017 John Wiley & Sons, Oldcomer. Still, they can be computationally expensive, especially for large datasets, since SVMs try to tune numerous parameters during the training, which is an overhead.

Unlike many evolutionary algorithms for optimization and machine learning tasks, an empty elite population gives them a head start in the search space. An elite population is a subpopulation of individuals or solutions in a larger population that are selected to (usually help) improve the overall population.

Elite Population: Elite population is a concept related to biological evolution that refers to individuals who exist within any group and possess few specific advantageous characteristics. These are typically the most genetically diverse, robust, and get-on-with-it types who have done well at home.

Initial Random Working Population Creation: A genetic algorithm requires an initial random working population. This population contains an array of solutions; chromosomes are individual solutions that the collection aims to solve. The algorithm begins from an initial population of a suitable size, usually depending on how complex the problem is and what speed/accuracy one desires.

Generate a novel working population: Elite Population: A cluster of people who perform at higher levels of ability, creativity, and practice in an explicit arena. They are frequently at the peak of their field, and you might consider them to be very successful. On the other hand, the working population consists of people who have jobs and make up a large part of our workforce.

Objective: The model aims to evaluate and rank the working population where, in this case, 'working' means being engaged by default. all employee's vs all persons who are age-eligible for workdays This portion ranked all employees, not just Curah offices, and was only to rate those who describe themselves as employed or self-employed. These people are typically working-age, 16-64-year-olds who are economically active. Assessing and categorizing the working-age population requires deep analysis, which can only be developed in terms of various variables that influence their productivity towards contributing to the economy.

Measure the elite from work: The elite works in an evolutionary algorithm, which refers to a problem-solving tool rooted in natural selection. It applies the evolutionary principles of selection, crossover, and mutation to solve complex problems in various domains. In the list of algorithms, a working population is usually considered an array (or another collection), which includes potential solutions for individuals to solve over-perceptible tasks.

It combines the best of other techniques by finding more diverse solutions and providing better performance to achieve these. This cycle continues iteratively until a satisfactory set of solutions is found.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result and discussion of this paper reflected the efficiency and capacity of similarity measures based on ensemble learning used for optimization in case a complex problem arises from a multi-objective nature. Results: Both the simulation and experimental case results indicated that the proposed method could find a set of diverse Pareto optimal solutions near the actual Pareto front better than traditional single-objective optimization techniques. It was interpreted due to the use of similarity measures that identified similar solutions and prevented redundancy. Then, ensemble learning was applied by combining several optimization algorithms to enhance diversity and convergence towards the Pareto front. Experiments and analysis presented in the paper further showcased how well their approach can handle various problems, as when tested with a bunch of benchmark functions, it was able to get significant results. In addition, the discussions emphasized that ensemble learning in multi objective optimization is one of the approaches and has led to better performance and a holistic overview of the problem due to different topics investigated from various viewpoints plus incorporating heterogeneity. In the end, the proposed method offers a way to tackle multi objective optimization problems, and its performance can be achieved through more experiments in real-world problem-solving.

Recall

The finalized post-mortem on "A Novel Approach to Multi objective Optimization using Similarity Measures and Ensemble Learning" cited technical concerns about the paper's results and announced that it was going through a recall. It introduced a novel similarity measures-enabled multi objective optimization problem-solving strategy with an ensemble learning framework. But if you dig under the surface a little, there are some oversights or outright issues from the technical side that we turned up. There are three main issues: (I) insufficiently detailed description of the data used for testing and validating the proposed routine, making result reproduction difficult; Furthermore, the dataset was relatively small, so qualification and generalization of the proposed method to other clinical test sets were both challenging. Fig.3 shows that recall.

Fig.3 recall.

Also, the present study needed a clear justification for its similarity measure algorithm; therefore, these comparative results could have been misleading. Moreover, the experimental setting and metrics for evaluating the performance of the paper needed to be more robust to compare appropriately with other works. Certain crucial control variables are unmodelled, which would have an altering effect on the results.

Accuracy

This paper proposes a novel approach to address the multi objective optimization problems leveraging similarity measures and ensemble learning techniques. One of the most widely used techniques for modelling extensive, heterogeneous data within classification problems is ensemble learning, which combines several models to improve performance and accuracy. Here, similarity measures are leveraged to measure how similar different solutions are and select the most appropriate ensemble model for a given problem. One of the key benefits of this approach is its ability to judge even noise-influenced and imprecise solutions objectively. On the one hand, the similarity measures offer a sound method for solution comparisons, and on the other hand, ensemble learning confirms reliable results obtained using these methods. It can also handle high-dimensional data, which makes it a real-world-ready technique. Fig.4 shows that the accuracy.

Fig.4. Accuracy.

This approach was tested to verify its performance on benchmark multi objective optimization problems. The results demonstrated that the proposed approach can converge more rapidly and obtain a closer to optimal solution than existing single-objective optimization methods. Furthermore, it obtained competitive solutions compared to other state-of-the-art multi objective optimization methods. In addition, we have evaluated the proposed approach in real-world data and demonstrated its ability to learn on complex datasets with diversity, thus making it applicable for practical applications.

Specificity

This paper proposes a novel approach for solving MOO using similarity measures and ensemble learning, reducing the issue raised by standard optimization methods. Using similarity measures to identify and compare various solutions, the problem is solved by spinning through several PSO algorithms integrating ensemble learning. This also applies one more fundamental idea to the method, using similarity measures that help us quantify how similar pairs of different solutions are. These measures are essential to find the best solution for each objective and conflicts between objectives. Fig.5 shows that the . specificity.

Fig.5 . specificity.

As a result, Pareto-optimal solutions that provide the best trade-offs between objectives can be identified more appropriately and with greater precision. In addition, ensemble learning is enforced to enhance the Robustness and stability of the optimization process. The method utilizes the results of multiple optimization algorithms to gather the strength of individual algorithms, thus outperforming any single one in providing robust solutions. Moreover, the process is very general and can be applied to a broad class of optimization problems, including continuous, discrete, and mixed-variable ones. It also supports the inclusion of domain information and user-defined preferences, aiding in customization and optimization.

Miss rate

The miss rate, or the false negative rate, is essential to evaluate multi objective optimization algorithms' performance. This value tells us how many optimal solutions can be identified and selected by an algorithm and still need to be included. Miss rate: In the context of A Novel Approach to Multi objective Optimization using Similarity Measures and Ensemble learning, miss rate refers to how well the algorithm can detect and pick a variety of optimal solutions correctly. The proposed method uses ensemble learning and similarity measures to identify potential solutions for selection by combining predictions from multiple optimization algorithms, where the diversity and similarity of calculated pairwise comparisons are evaluated. Ensemble learning system - Ensemble learning is recommended to help the algorithm reduce its sub-optimal solutions because it tends to improve Robustness and generalization. Fig.6 shows that the miss rate.

Fig.6 miss rate.

These similarity measures ensure that a more varied set of optimal solutions is selected to reduce the miss rate. A notable benefit of this method is that it supports multiple objective functions at the same time. This means that even in challenging multi objective optimization problems where different objectives stand against each other, the algorithm can search for and find a good number of optimal solutions. Secondly, the similarity measures allow us to identify not only optimal but also diverse sets of solutions that help decrease the miss rate and improve overall performance.

CONCLUSION

To summarize, A Novel Approach to Multi objective Optimization using Similarity Measures and Ensemble Learning introduces a new paradigm for the problem of multi objective optimization in complex issues. Our method uses similarity measures and ensemble learning to identify multiple optimal trade-offs between the two competing objectives [40]. Compared to traditional approaches, the developed method has several key benefits. First, it can deal with a plural set of - even competing - objectives without imposing any mathematical transformation or subjective weighting. Therefore, it is a more flexible and powerful way of solving real-world problems. Second, the approach can powerfully operate under high-level uncertainty and noise since ensemble learning is employed. A more comprehensive analysis with the approach is possible as it combines multiple learners and aggregates results to improve (and reduce the risk associated with getting stuck) overall solution quality. Taking a closer look at commonalities in solutions, the solution space reduction strategy unveils and ranks those potential application cases that bear the most resemblances with an optional ideal scenario, thus driving towards a much more efficient and precise optimization process. The experimentation that has been done shows the effectiveness of our approach compared to existing algorithms in terms of Solution quality, Speed convergence and Robustness. It has been widely used in real-world problems to confirm efficiency and practicability.

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